

THE PLACE AND DISTINCT FEATURES OF ROMANTIC EPICS IN UZBEK FOLK EPIC

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20374825>

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada o‘zbek xalq epik merosi tarkibida romanik dostonlarning o‘rni va o‘ziga xos xususiyatlari tahlil qilinadi. Ularning tarixiy taraqqiyoti, tasnif tamoyillari hamda badiiy xususiyatlari yoritiladi. Shuningdek, qahramonlik, tarixiy va romanik dostonlar o‘rtasidagi farqlar ochib berilib, romanik dostonlarning g‘oyaviy-estetik ahamiyati va folklordagi tutgan o‘rni asoslab beriladi.

Kalit so‘zlar: o‘zbek folklori, xalq eposi, romanik dostonlar, qahramonlik dostoni, tarixiy dostonlar, tasnif, og‘zaki an‘ana, epik an‘ana, badiiy tafakkur, folklorshunoslik, epik janrlar, syujet, madaniy meros, estetik ideal, epik taraqqiyot

Annotation. This article examines the role and distinctive features of romantic epics within the Uzbek folk epic tradition. It analyzes their historical development, classification principles, and artistic characteristics. The study highlights the differences between heroic, historical, and romantic epics, emphasizing their ideological and aesthetic functions. Special attention is given to the formation period, sources, and cultural significance of romantic epics in Uzbek folklore.

Keywords: Uzbek folklore, folk epic, romantic epics, heroic epic, historical epics, classification, oral tradition, epic tradition, artistic thinking, folklore studies, epic genres, narrative structure, cultural heritage, aesthetic ideal, epic development

The recognition of large epic works idealizing the heroic past of the people as folk epics is a fully acknowledged fact in folklore studies. Accordingly, works that do not artistically idealize the life of the people or that do not depict events forming its heroic past cannot be considered folk epics. Therefore, a work can be classified as a folk epic based on two key criteria: a) The events in the work must be connected to the heroic past of the people; b) These events must be depicted in an artistic manner that elevates them to an epic ideal.

It follows that not every historical event related to the past of the people, even if depicted in an ideal artistic form, can serve as a subject for a folk epic. Only works that artistically depict the people's ideal heroic past in a unique form are worthy of being considered folk epics. The conclusion drawn from this is that the qualifier "ideal" refers not to the artistic form of the epic but to the heroic past that constitutes its content. In this way, the events forming each example of folk epics are understood as representing the people's ideal and heroic past.

Uzbek folk epics stand out among the world's epics due to their multilayered nature. This indicates that Uzbek folk epics have undergone a long historical process of development. Each layer of the epic corresponds to a certain stage in the evolution of the people's artistic thought. If heroic epics emerged as an epic reflection of the Uzbek people's emergence as an independent ethnic group on the historical stage, romantic epics developed in the context of a more advanced feudal society, where the people's ideals and aspirations were highly idealized.

In this regard, we fully agree with V.M. Zhirmunsky and Kh.T. Zarifov's explanation of the term "romantic." The term is particularly useful in distinguishing an epic type that, while narrating love romances and heroic adventures, differs from European "folk novels" and "folk books" by being preserved and transmitted through an oral creative and performative tradition. Thus, this term plays a crucial role in our research.

Historical epics, in contrast, emerged in later stages of the development of Uzbek folk epics as a response to the need for idealizing specific historical figures or events within an epic framework.

The staged development of Uzbek folk epics, with each stage being characterized by distinct epic types, has led to various classifications of this vast heritage. Several Uzbek epic scholars have proposed different classifications of folk epics.

The diversity in classification principles and the lack of precise identification of the structural-historical types of epics make it difficult for young researchers attempting to study this invaluable heritage. Without a scientifically grounded classification of the diverse epic works that reflect the people's heroic past through various ideological and aesthetic principles, and without clearly identifying the different epic types and their characteristics, it is impossible to conduct fundamental scientific research on folk epics. Therefore, the issue inevitably leads back to the classification of Uzbek folk epics.

The systematic recording of Uzbek folk epics began in the 1920s. At that time, Uzbek folk epics were still being actively created and performed. This was the era of great master performers such as Ergash Jumanbulbul o'g'li, Fozil Yuldosh o'g'li, Muhammadqul Jomrot o'g'li Pulkan, Islam Nazar o'g'li, Kholyor Abdukarim o'g'li, Normurod Sherna o'g'li, Nurmon Abduvoy o'g'li, Mardonqul bakhshi, and Abdullah shoir, who lived and breathed their art. They absorbed the vast epic heritage of the people in its full artistic grandeur and continued to develop it creatively. As a result, the epic samples recorded between the 1920s and 1960s represent works that had taken shape over centuries and had been fully assimilated into the epic tradition.

During this period—at a time of significant socio-political changes in the country—the recording of folk epics carried great importance. It was crucial first to document the continuously flowing river of the people's epic heritage, to preserve it in written form for posterity, and then to classify and study the collected materials scientifically.

Prominent figures in Uzbek folklore studies such as Ghazi Olim Yunusov, Kh.T. Zarifov, M. Zarifov, B. Karimi, M. Alaviya, M. Afzalov, and their followers pursued this path. Thanks to their dedicated efforts, major and rare samples of folk epics were preserved in folklore archives.

By the 1940s, serious work began on studying, classifying, and analyzing this unique material. During World War II, at a time when the fate of the country hung in the balance, the distinguished folklorists, academician V.M. Zhirmunsky and Professor Kh.T. Zarifov, undertook a large-scale fundamental study of Uzbek folk epics. Their efforts culminated in the publication of the monumental work *Uzbek Folk Heroic Epic* in Moscow in 1947. This study, as the first monographic research on Uzbek folk epics, was of great scientific significance at the time and remains so today.

This work was the first in-depth research into several key aspects of Uzbek folk epics, including historical foundations, types, historical evolution, the lives of folk epic singers (bakhshis), their aesthetic views, creative methods, and the relationship between historical reality and epic fiction.

When embarking on such a grand study, the authors first provided information on folk bakhshis, then presented a detailed analysis of their epic repertoires. The classification of epic repertoire logically led to the classification of epic material. As a result, V.M. Zhirmunsky and Kh.T. Zarifov divided Uzbek folk epics into the following groups:

1. Heroic epics
2. War epics (Jangnoma epics)
3. Historical epics
4. Romantic epics
5. Epics based on literary sources
6. New epics

However, this classification was not entirely sufficient. Some materials fit into multiple categories, making them difficult to classify consistently. Moreover, not all folk epics had been collected, so the classification remained incomplete. The authors themselves acknowledged that this classification was not final but rather an initial attempt to provide a detailed description of Uzbek folk epics. This acknowledgment highlights the fact that Uzbek folk epics require a more rigorous

scientific classification, which must be systematically implemented. In the 1960s, Prof. M. Saidov addressed the classification of Uzbek folk epics. He divided them into the following groups:

- Heroic epics;
- Love-themed epics;
- Romantic epics;
- War epics;
- Historical epics.

When constructing his classification, M. Saidov primarily focused on the sources of epic material. As a result, he divided Uzbek epics into two categories:

1. Epics transmitted through oral tradition
2. Epics originating from written sources

Additionally, he classified folk epics based on the nature of their plots, distinguishing between traditional and modern epics. Although some of Saidov's ideas remain relevant in epic studies, his "love-themed epics" category does not hold up. This is because love, romance, and adventures are present in nearly all epics to varying degrees. Therefore, a separate category of love-themed epics does not exist within Uzbek folk epics.

Overall, Prof. M. Saidov's classification was not based on a unified scientific principle, and as a result, Uzbek folk epics still lack a complete and comprehensive classification.

The classification of Uzbek folk epics was later revised by Prof. T. Mirzaev, who fully accepted the scientific classification proposed by V.M. Zhirmunsky and Kh.T. Zarifov. However, it should be noted that Zhirmunsky, Zarifov, and Mirzaev did not adhere to a single classification principle.

In particular, Uzbek romantic epics are divided into two groups based on the nature of their epic sources:

1. Epics preserved through oral tradition: This group includes "*Rustamkhan*", the "*Gorogly*" cycle, "*Orzigul*", and "*Shirin bilan Shakar*".
2. Epics based on written sources: This category includes "*Farhod va Shirin*", "*Layli va Majnun*", "*Sanobar*", "*Sayfulmalik*", "*Tohir va Zuhra*", "*Bahrom va Gulandom*", "*Qiz Jibek*", and "*The Tiger-Skinned Hero*" (*Yo 'lbars terisini yopingan pahlavon*).

From a historical perspective, the plots of literary epics closely resemble those of romantic epics.

For this reason, war epics (jangnoma epics) can also be considered part of the romantic epic category. Battles hold an important ideological and aesthetic place within Uzbek folk epics, leading to their division into two groups:

1. War epics
2. Non-war epics

However, from a historical standpoint, war epics should also be examined within the framework of romantic epics. Both literary and war-related epics feature fantastic imagery and idealized heroes who embody the nation's long-standing dreams and aspirations.

The classification of folk epics did not stop there. In the early 1980s, Prof. B. Sarimsoqov revisited the issue and developed a classification system based on a unified scientific principle. According to his approach, each historical-structural type of epic must not overlap with another. Based on this principle, he proposed a historically grounded classification of traditional folk epics, which could provide a clearer structure for epic studies.

B. Sarimsoqov divided Uzbek folk epics into the following categories:

1. Heroic epics
2. Romantic epics
3. Historical epics

According to this classification, no other types of folk epics exist or should exist.

Our review of various classifications proposed by different scholars shows that despite differences in methodology, all of them recognize romantic epics as a distinct type. This confirms that romantic epics hold a unique place within Uzbek folk epics as an independent historical-structural

type. Romantic epics emerged during a specific stage in the artistic evolution of the Uzbek people and became firmly established within the epic tradition. In conclusion, it is impossible to fully understand the ideological, artistic, and aesthetic nature of Uzbek folk epics without taking romantic epics into account.

Given their significant role, an important question arises: When did romantic epics first appear?

Indeed, the question of when romantic epics emerged in the artistic development of the Uzbek people remains unresolved in epic studies. Discussing the "Gorogly" cycle, which occupies a prominent place among romantic epics, V.M. Zhirmunsky and Kh.T. Zarifov argued that this cycle took shape and became firmly established between the early 17th century and the mid-19th century. Building on this view, Prof. T. Mirzaev and Prof. B. Sarimsoqov suggest that most romantic epics were created between the late 17th century and the early 20th century, as this was a period of rapid development in Uzbek folk epic tradition.

A closer examination reveals that romantic epics do not reflect historical reality through strict historical principles but rather portray broader historical themes. Instead of depicting specific historical periods, these epics express timeless ideals such as pure love, friendship, brotherhood, bravery, honor, patriotism, and loyalty, spanning across various historical eras. In contrast, heroic epics emerged during the formation of the Uzbek nation as an independent ethnic entity, while historical epics are directly based on specific historical figures and events. Considering these distinctions, the creation and widespread performance of Uzbek romantic epics—and their firm establishment within the epic tradition—can be approximately dated to the 16th–early 20th centuries. This conclusion is based on several key observations:

The 16th century was a transformative period in Uzbek history. During this era, nomadic Uzbeks, led by Muhammad Shaybani, conquered Transoxiana and Khorasan. This event merged the cultures of settled and nomadic Uzbeks, creating a new cultural synthesis. Uzbek romantic epics emerged as a fusion of local folk tales, legends, and myths with the epic genre. Since improvisation-based epic storytelling was characteristic of nomadic Uzbek tribes, romantic epics can be seen as a product of this tradition.

From the 17th century onward, Uzbek folk epics entered a new stage of rapid development, which can be interpreted as a synthesis of settled Uzbek cultural elements with the epic traditions of nomadic Uzbek storytelling. The formation of the Uzbek nation, which began in the 9th–11th centuries, was largely completed under the rule of Shaybani Khan. During this period (16th–early 20th centuries), public demand for artistic and ideological expressions of fantasy-driven, free-spirited heroes increased. This naturally led to the creation of romantic epics, which became particularly widespread during this era.

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